

**TRENDS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE STOCK MARKET AND ITS
IMPACT ON THE TRANSFORMATION OF COMMERCIAL BANKS****FOND BOZORINING RIVOJLANISH TENDENSIYALARI VA UNING
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Annotatsiya**

Eng. - This article analyzes the transformation processes of commercial banks, in particular the need to privatize banks with a high state share, and the implementation of this process through stock market instruments. Also, it emphasizes how the stock market serves as a key platform for attracting private investment, improving transparency, and enhancing corporate governance in the banking sector.

Uzb. - Ushbu maqolada tijorat banklarining transformatsiya jarayonlari, xususan, davlat ulushi yuqori bo'lgan banklarni xususiylashtirish zarurati va bu jarayonni fond bozori vositalari orqali amalga oshirish tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, u fond bozori xususiy investitsiyalarni jalb qilish, shaffoflikni oshirish va bank sektorida korporativ boshqaruvni takomillashtirish uchun asosiy platforma bo'lib xizmat qilishiga urg'u beradi.

**Keywords:
Kalit so'zlar:**

❖ *stock market, commercial bank, digital economy, stock, bond, securities.*

❖ *fond bozori, tijorat banki, raqamli iqtisodiyot, aksiyalar, obligatsiyalar, qimmatli qog'ozlar.*

Introduction.

The financial sector plays a vital role in the growth and development of any economy. In recent years, Uzbekistan has achieved substantial progress in reforming its financial system to enhance public access to financial services and stimulate economic growth. The adoption of modern banking technologies has already had a positive impact on local banking system and is now recognized as an integral part of the national economy. This trend is not only relevant to Uzbekistan but also reflects a global shift. The broad implementation of digital technologies across the country demonstrates the adaptability of both society and the economy to change. Moreover,

digitalization significantly accelerates everyday processes for the majority of citizens. Banks are introducing innovative technologies into their operations to attract more customers and ensure their future financial stability. One of the main tools influencing the implementation of these changes is the stock market.

It is important to understand the role of commercial banks in the financial sector. Commercial banks act as intermediaries, connecting savers and borrowers, and play a vital role in providing financing to the real sector of the economy. In Uzbekistan, commercial banks have played an important role in stimulating economic growth and expanding access to financial services. The

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 No. PD-60 "On the Development Strategy of the New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" provides for the completion of transformation processes in commercial banks with a state share and an increase in the share of the private sector to 60 percent in bank assets by the end of 2026 [1]. However, the transformation of commercial banks was a gradual process, and the development of the stock market played a key role in this process.

Literature review.

U. Sharpe, G. Alexander, and J. Bailey have studied stock markets as an integral part of the financial system that facilitates the purchase and sale of securities and the exchange of financial assets [2]. Stock markets are one of the key components of developed countries' economies, influencing financial institutions, corporations, national economic sectors, and global economic processes.

According to the Russian economist E. Zhukov, the popularity of the stock market is influenced by the legal status of stock exchanges. He identifies several types: public-law, private, and mixed [3]. Public-law stock exchanges are primarily regulated by the state and are responsible for developing regulatory documents and overseeing the execution of exchange transactions. In privately organized stock exchanges, typically established as joint-stock companies, securities trading is carried out independently in accordance with the law. Mixed stock exchanges are also organized as joint-stock companies, with at least 50% of the authorized capital owned by the state.

According to F. Khamidova, the stock market acts as a locomotive that unites all financial market participants and plays a significant role in global economic relations. Currently, securities trading is considered the most widespread form of directing investments [4]. This is because, for direct foreign investment, investors must accumulate large

financial resources. On the stock market, however, investors direct their funds based on the value of securities of joint-stock companies.

In the research F. Mukhamedov emphasizes that securities trading systems are a set of infrastructural institutions that form the environment and relationships related to securities trading [5]. Today, in the global economy, stock markets can be classified into global and regional structures. Each form of exchange is composed of market relations among various entities and is typically specialized according to the production or service sectors of the issuers involved.

One of the factors of the rapid digitalization process and, accordingly, the transformation of the banking sector is the spread of the novel coronavirus infection COVID-19. It was the restrictions introduced under its influence that contributed to the transition to the online space [6].

According to Sagynbekov, the digitalization process in Russia is not going as fast as abroad [7]. Russia lags behind leading foreign countries in terms of the level of use of innovations in the digital field.

L. Demurchyan notes in his research that digital technologies are currently developing rapidly in the banking sector of the economy, and this applies not only to Russia, but also to almost the entire world [8]. More than 85% of users of banking services use mobile banking applications for the purpose of remote management of their finances, as well as constant access to them.

Methodology.

In order to study in more detail the impact of the stock market on the transformation of commercial banks in Uzbekistan, we analyzed the data provided by the Russian Stock Exchange "Toshkent" from 2020 till 2024. This study provides a substantive analysis of changes and comparative analysis of some parameters. The main information base for the study is the

materials of the Republican Stock Exchange “Tashkent”.

Analysis and results.

The stock market provides a platform for companies to raise capital and for investors to buy and sell shares of these companies. By providing an alternative source of funding for commercial banks, the stock market helps reduce their dependence on traditional sources of funding such as deposits. This not only increases the stability of the financial sector, but also allows commercial banks to expand their operations and offer a wider range of financial services to their customers. In addition, the stock market provides commercial banks with an opportunity to improve their corporate governance and risk management practices. Listing shares on the stock exchange requires companies to adhere to higher standards of transparency and accountability, which can contribute to improving the overall quality of the financial sector [9].

Banks in Uzbekistan began to reach the peak of the transformation process in 2022. The volume of transactions in the securities market of commercial banks on the Republican Stock Exchange “Tashkent” over the past 3

years was equal to the total amount of annual trading in securities by banks. The impact of the securities market on financing modernization and access to high technologies is due to the fact that the stock market mechanism allows [10]:

- a) to attract the necessary financial resources at a lower price as a result of the scale effect in a wider market;
- b) to acquire shares of high-tech companies and participate in their activities and corporate management, giving investors the opportunity to diversify and share risks;
- c) to carry out mergers and acquisitions of business structures.

It should be emphasized that the savings accumulated in banks reach the real sector either in the form of loans provided by banks to enterprises, or through their investment in shares. In the latter case, the stock market becomes the most important mechanism for the formation, implementation and redistribution of investments. At the same time, the functioning of the stock market cannot be separated from the activities of banks, which are primarily associated with the financial market model of Uzbekistan, which can be classified as bank-oriented.

Picture 1. Quantity of completed transactions on the Republican Stock Exchange “Tashkent” from 2020-2024 [11]

Figure 1 presents the number of trade transactions and their annual growth rate in percentage terms on the "Toshkent" Republican Stock Exchange for the period from 2020 to 2024. In 2020, the number of trade transactions amounted to 35,9 thousand, while by 2024, this figure had increased almost tenfold, reaching 443,8 thousand. The graph shows a consistent upward trend in the number

of trades, with a particularly sharp surge observed in 2023. This indicates a rise in market participants, technological advancement, or the positive impact of socio-economic factors. This situation reflects the influence of the stock market on accelerating the transformation processes of commercial banks (see Table 1).

Table 1

The share of sectors in the amount of transactions in the stock market in 2020-2024 (billion soums) [11]

Sectors	Years									
	2020		2021		2022		2023		2024	
	Amount	%	Amount	%	Amount	%	Amount	%	Amount	%
Banks	326,67	56,5	312,61	24,8	2308,67	47,9	971,97	35,8	6423,4	32,8
Leasing	4,23	0,7	0,41	0,0	15,12	0,3	13,9	0,5	0,0	0,0
Industry	13,59	2,4	95,14	7,5	53,96	1,1	108,45	4,0	12235,4	62,6
Agro-industry	44,85	7,8	40,18	3,2	237,93	4,9	597,74	22,0	20,9	0,1
Communications	0,12	0,0	0,32	0,0	0,07	0,0	37,0	1,4	3,7	0,0
Insurance	49,06	8,5	36,42	2,9	87,13	1,8	77,23	2,8	26,8	0,1
Construction	15,99	2,8	641,17	50,9	1924,35	40,0	17,76	0,7	18,5	0,1
Transport	2,22	0,4	0,03	0,0	0,02	0,0	66,54	2,5	252,8	1,3
Energy	14,16	2,5	98,92	7,8	19,65	0,4	119,45	4,4	32,4	0,2
Others	107,26	18,6	35,31	2,8	169,31	3,5	702,7	25,9	546,2	2,8
Total	578,15	100	1260,51	100	4816,21	100	2712,74	100	19560,0	100

The major issuers on the stock market are commercial banks, whose securities accounted for a significant portion of the total transaction volume during the analyzed period. In 2024, the most liquid securities belonged to joint-stock companies operating in the following sectors: commercial banks (6423,4 billion UZS or 32,8%), construction (12235,4 billion UZS or 62,6%), and transport (252,8 billion UZS or 1,3%). This situation reflects the significant role of commercial banks in the capital market and highlights the deepening transformation processes within the sector. Total transaction volume indicates their active participation in attracting investments through the stock market. Despite the construction sector dominating the sustained presence of banks among the most liquid issuers suggests ongoing

efforts to diversify funding sources, improve transparency, and align with market-based financial mechanisms. This dynamic underscores the gradual but steady transformation of commercial banks from traditional lending institutions into more market-oriented entities that leverage capital markets to finance growth and strengthen their financial stability.

Conclusion.

In recent years, the reforms carried out in Uzbekistan’s banking sector—particularly the privatization of banks with state shares, digitalization, strengthening corporate governance principles, and ensuring transparency—have significantly enhanced the integration of banks with financial markets.

The fact that commercial banks accounted for 32.8% of the total trading volume on the stock market in 2024 clearly demonstrates their effective use of the capital market to attract financial resources.

The active participation of banks in the stock market is driven by several key factors. Firstly, it allows banks to attract long-term capital, which in turn helps expand their lending capacity. Secondly, banks that have transitioned to a joint-stock company structure aim to gain investor confidence through the stock market while also ensuring their financial stability. Thirdly, operating in the stock market encourages banks to maintain transparency in financial reporting, improve risk management systems, and strengthen strategic governance.

Moreover, the development of the stock market is closely tied to digital technologies.

The extensive use of information technology in the bank transformation process increases their market entry speed, operational efficiency, and investment attractiveness. This, in turn, contributes to the institutional development not only of the banking system but of the entire financial sector.

In conclusion, the active presence of commercial banks in the stock market represents a key strategic direction in their transformation process. This process enables banks to align with market economy demands, form stable sources of financing, and deepen their integration with international financial institutions. Therefore, the role and importance of the stock market in accelerating transformation within the banking sector will continue to grow.

References:

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated 28.01.2022 No. PD-60 "On the Development Strategy of new Uzbekistan for 2022-2026".
2. Шарп У., Александер Г., Бэйли Дж. Инвестиции: Пер. с англ.-ИНФРА-М, 2001. -XII, 1028 с., с 8.
3. Жуков Е.Ф. Ценные бумаги и фондовые рынки: Учебное пособие-М.: ЮНИТИ, 1995-С.198.
4. Хамидова Ф.А. Анализ и пути привлечения портфельных инвестиций в приватизированные предприятия: автореферат дисс... к.э.н. - Ташкент, 2009.-19 с.
5. Ф.Мухамедов. Ўзбекистонда қимматли қўғозлар бозори савдо тизимларини ривожлантириш йўналишлари. Иқтисодиёт фанлари доктори (DSc) диссертацияси автореферати. – Т.: ТМИ, 2019. – 7 бет.
6. Nielsen Online & International Telecommunications Union, 2020. - URL: <https://nielsen.online/> (дата обращения: 11.03.2022)
7. Сагынбекова А.С. Цифровая экономика: понятия, перспективы, тенденции развития // Международный научно-технический журнал «Теория. Практика. Инновации» (электронный журнал). №4 (28). Апрель 2018.
8. Демурчян Л.Р. Трансформация банковского сектора в условиях цифровизации // Инновации и инвестиции. – 2022. – №3. – С. 91-95.
9. www.tadviser.ru
10. www.quote.rbc.ru
11. www.uzse.uz